

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

WAYS OF FORMATION OF TERMS IN THE SCIENTIFIC STYLE IN THE AZERBAIJAN LANGUAGE

Aliyeva M.

To the Institute of Linguistics named after Nasimi, ANAS

Abstract

The ways of the emergence of terms in the scientific style in the Azerbaijani language are characterized in the article. The special lexicon, which is the basis of the scientific style, mainly enriches this lexical layer and becomes a technical system there. The main lexical units of the language vocabulary are elaborated in various fields of the scientific style and enrich the terminological layer. Therefore, the level of development and richness of the language is mostly related to innovations in the fields of science. The development of science and technology leads to the establishment of new fields and directions, the merging of different fields of science, the creation of new terms and concepts. Therefore, a comprehensive research in the term creation process has been conducted in a scientific style. It is obvious that the potential possibilities of the language are widely used in the term-creation process. The semantics of the word expands in some cases and semantic conversion and semantic compression occur in other cases. As a result, a scientific research plays a leading role in enriching the terminology of the field with new terms.

Keywords: style, semantics, scientific style, concept, term, lexicon, morphological layer.

The special lexicon, which is the basis of the scientific style, enriches this lexical layer and becomes a technical system there. The main lexical units of the language vocabulary are elaborated in various fields of the scientific style and enrich the terminological layer. Therefore, the level of development and richness of the language is mostly related to innovations in the fields of science. The development of science and technology leads to the establishment of new fields and directions, the merging of different fields of science, the creation of new terms and concepts. Therefore, there is a need to comprehensively research the term creation process in a scientific manner. New concepts emerging with the development of separate fields of science impact the formation of terminologies of various fields and their term creation process. The development of linguistic units from this point of view, which is the main factor in the formation of the scientific style, is created as a set of terminological systems related to various fields of science. The creation of scientific works related to the development of separate fields of science in different periods was a universal phenomenon and created a new historical turn in the development of the literary language. Literary language is enriched due to new styles. Scientific style is one of the main directions that enrich literary language. As the scientific style is syncretic in nature and common words, term-specific words and terms are used in unity in this style. Scientific and technical progress promotes the rapid development of science. The differentiation and integration of sciences in the years of independence led to the creation of new fields of science. Aviation, Informatics, Logistics, Economics, Political Science have especially been formed as independent sciences in modern times. Science fields include exact sciences (Physics, Mathematics), natural sciences (Biology, Geography), social sciences (History, Linguistics, etc.). All these fields of science have their own language characteristics. At the same time, these sciences

combine at certain points and form the scientific style. Scientific discoveries, scientific theory, concepts related to laws and principles are called as an element of the development of separate fields of science. The development of sciences is a form of thinking resulting from research of various nature. Concepts formed as a result of research as a product of thinking activity are called scientific language units. In all cases, this naming process is continuously active in the researched scientific fields.

The emergence of new fields of science develops the literary language. The development of scientific fields leads to the emergence of new concepts and phenomena. The main linguistic units of scientific style are terms. Taking this into account, the terminological lexicon of scientific works created in scientific style in the Azerbaijani language can be divided into two groups according to the sources of creation: terms created due to the internal capabilities of the language; terms created due to borrowed words.

The development of scientific fields accelerates the dynamism of the terminological base. The expression of emerging concepts also affects the sources of origin of terms. A. Gurbanov writes: "There is no language and there cannot be any language in the world that expresses each concept with separate special words. A new word is not often sought for the expression of new concepts that appear in connection with development, but one or another phenomenon is expressed by changing the meaning of an existing word in the language." (3, p. 389)

S. Jafarov writes: "The process of formation of words by lexical method differs from the process of formation by morphological and syntactic method mainly in terms of its simplicity. However, this seemingly simple way is really very complicated." (1, p. 135) The lexical meaning of common word and the semantic volume of the word expand as a result of various semantic changes in the scientific style. For

example, a word "mouthpiece" is used as a common word in the meaning "smaller than mouth". The following terms were created: "the part of the flower's stamen separated from the upper side" in the field of botany, and "connecting part of oil pipes" in technology, the terms "chain chemical reactions" based on the word "chain" in the field of Chemistry - by regeneration of an active particle without interruption which consists of an intermediate reaction product it forms that cause chemical transformations in a large number of molecules or nuclei of the original substance.

When comparing common words and terms, it is clear that "a term must have a limited and fixed content unlike an ordinary word or phrase. This content must belong to the term regardless of the context, whereas the meaning of an ordinary word is determined by the context." (8, p. 18).

Some common words are used in the scientific style as scientific-technical lexemes both directly in the first nominative sense and in the later acquired sense. Semantically modified common words are used as one of the main methods of term creation in the development of the scientific style in the Azerbaijani language. For example, the common meaning of the word "Memory" is to remember, to keep in mind and "memory" in informatics means a functional part that ensures the reception, preservation and transmission of data in a computing system. (6, p. 36) The terms "memory device", memory slot, memory zone, memory volume, memory system were also created related to this term. In the process of terminating common words, the transfer of meaning is realized due to the generality of the sign expressed by the word. The basic meanings of the terms in the fields of science are referred to. It may coincide with the original meaning of the common words in the creation of the main meaning in some cases. However, the original meaning is not reflected in the expression of the term in the field of science in some cases. The original meaning is not preserved, a completely new meaning is created. The term-creation tendency based on the internal capabilities of our language has been strengthened by giving additional meaning to the common words. Common words are widely used in the formation of military-field concepts. For example, division, ceasefire, fighter, drill, trailer (military), welding, etc.

In reality, there are many things, subjects, objects and they are named. There are certain relationships between things and subjects. As they can be similar in form, subject, space, time, etc., they can also connect with relationships. Associatively comparing objects to each other does not equate them and does not eliminate the differences in their essence. However, similarity and associative analogy causes different subjects and objects to be named with the same words. As a result, the common word takes a new meaning. This phenomenon mostly occurs in a term creation process. The semantic method is distinguished by its productivity in term creation, unlike in ordinary word creation. Its reason is the terminization of common words included in the vocabulary of the language.

The differentiation in the meaning of words is manifested in the naming of concepts in different ways in relation to their general meanings in the process of terminization in a scientific style. These differences do not end with the fact that common words belong to homonymic meanings in their basic and derived meanings. Sometimes these lexemes can enter the scientific language only in relation to derived meanings and in this case, differences can arise in the meanings they express. Common words can be divided into two groups according to the feature of expressing concepts in the fields of science: 1. The common word is used without any change in the fields of science that form the basis of the scientific style. This process is mostly observed in various fields of construction, music, jewelry, pedagogy, soil science, cooking, botany, medicine, animal husbandry, mineralogy and agriculture.

2. A common word is used in the fields of science that form the basis of the scientific style, moving away from its original meaning. Common words in the fields of Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Geology, and Informatics are terminized by moving away from their previous meanings.

The terms that make up the terminological lexicon of the scientific style are used both as a common word and as a term. The terminological function of common words is distinguished by its relevance in all fields of science.

V.P. Danilenko writes: "The change of the scientific language, its development is determined by the processes taking place in the general literary language as well as by the characteristics of the development of science in different historical periods. Three independent layers can be distinguished in the lexicon of the scientific language: 1) non-terminological lexicon (main and auxiliary words of the language); 2) universal lexicon (special words of scientific communication); it includes special words used in various fields of science. The number of words in this layer is constantly increasing in modern times thanks to the integration and differentiation of sciences; 3) special terminological lexicon (special words of a specific terminological system)" [7, p. 64].

The vernacular should be taken as a basis for the expression of the phenomena in modern times while seeking reciprocity that have arisen in connection with separate fields of science, as well as in a broader sense, related to the social structure. The basis for creating a new word or term is the use of a morphological tool. Morphological means are not only suffixes. Each word also functions as a morphological tool when referring to the belonging of the word's part of speech. Morphological word modification is the creation of a new word by changing the form of an existing word using various formal means. Since two or more words are joined together in word modification in the form of a compound word, the change of form takes place in a slightly different way. The change of the form of the existing word often takes an unobvious form in abbreviation. The following suffixes were widely used in term creation by morphological method: -lıq, -lik, -luq, -lük; -çl, -çl, -çu, -çü, -ıcl, -ıcl, -ucuc, -üclü, -ma, -

mə, -li, -li, -lu, -lü, -cıq, -ıq, -ik, -uq, -ük, -ük, -ənək, -sız, -ı, -ılı, -çək, -daş, -ki, -ış, etc. For example, computer scientist, developer (designer), communicativity, discursiveness, textuality, intertextuality, etc. Term creation terms can be grouped according to different models by using the morphological method in scientific style: 1) root + suffix; 2) root + suffix + suffix; 3) root + suffix + suffix + suffix;

The most useful and important method of term creation in a scientific text is a syntactic method. S. Sadigova writes: "Combining two or more words in term creation and expressing the scientific concept in the form of compound words and word combinations play an important role in the enrichment of terminology. The analysis of the terminological system shows that the syntactic method is of special importance in the creation of terms related to various fields of science and technology." (9, p. 68) This method is more widely used in the scientific style. The syntactic method is productive in the generation of terms in the terminology of all the fields. When researchers compare term creation methods according to their productivity in their studies of different field terminologies, it becomes clear that the terms formed by the syntactic method in the scientific style form an important part of the terminology of this field. A similar situation is observed in other Turkic languages. There is also a large number of syntactically formed terms in English (German, French, etc.). Its main reason is the relationship between the new terms created and the existing terms. Here, the scope of the scientific concept expands, it acquires new characteristics and also the phenomenon of the formation of its types takes place. This is more evident in terms that are in the form of word combinations. According to A.V. Superanskaya, terms were created in almost three ways: 1) setting restrictions on the processing of a common word, determining its meaning in a definitive way - terminization; 2) creating term-word combinations, term-phrases from the words of the language; 3) naming new concepts with new words - term-formation (10, p. 114).

Symbols, signs, graphs, diagrams are also typical for the scientific style of a number of fields (for example, Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Theoretical Mechanics, etc.) in scientific text parts of some fields.

The terms created by the syntactic method in the scientific style can be divided into three main groups: 1) those in the form of compound words; 2) those in the form of double words; 3) those in the form of word combinations.

The terms that are made up in the form of a compoundword in the scientific style can be divided into two main groups according to the component structure of the compound word: a) those with both components being a simple word; b) one of the components of which is a derivative word. Of course, the existence of terms with a compound word structure formed by the combination of three components cannot be excluded.

Compound word-form terms which components are simple words are made based on the "simple word+simple word" or "root+root" model. For example, supersystem (super+system), subprogram (sub+program), semiprogram (semi+program), subcolony (sub+colony), revenue account (revenue+account), etc.

Compound word-form terms formed by combining two simple words without taking any sign are a minority. The components of such terms formed by the syntactic method can be both words of the language itself and borrowed words. It is possible to classify these terms according to which part of speech the components belong to. For example, adverb+noun (subsystem), number+noun (semi-program, semi-finished product), etc.

There are a lot of words among the terms in the form of compound words that are created by means of the method where one word is derivative, while another is simple. For example, one-product, one-field, taxation, machine-building, presentation, damage, idleness, etc.

The derivative component of the compound-word type term is made up of various suffixes. For example, "-li, -li, -lu, -lü": one-field, verbal noun suffix "-ma, -mə": " idleness, short circuit, burning in fire, etc.

Such terms of compound word type are recorded in the scientific style that one of their part has received a modifying suffix, not a correcting one. For example, hired to work, hired per day, out-of-shift, unplanned (losses), inter-field, etc.

When a number of terms are formed syntactically, one of their components is a participle. For example, self-discharging, self-walker, employer, buyer, consignor, victim, number collector. It is interesting that the terms that are included in the content of participle formed with the participle suffixes "-mış, -miş, -muş, -müş" which are hardly found in other field terminologies are recorded in the economics terminology. For example, minted (coin).

Terms with a complex structure, combined with a hyphen and formed in a double word pattern are also used in the scientific style. These terms are not widespread in field terminologies. The above-mentioned structural terms are used in economics, finance, art and commercial terminologies. For example, *accounts*, *exhibition-fair*, *exhibition-competition*, *import-export*, *importation-exportation*, etc. One of the main features of the double-word pattern is the repetition of words. The components of words from this model are words close to each other in meaning in terminology. The term "accounts" is formed according to the double-word model.

Phrasal terms are common terms that are formed syntactically and they are the leading functional units in scientific style due to their functionality. Words are combined to form sentences and sayings in the scientific language. These combinations are formed according to the patterns of word combinations. All types of definite word combinations and verb combinations in the Azerbaijani language take part in the creation of term-word combinations. Abbreviations, contractions or short forms are used in

scientific style. Both abbreviations and contractions are used in Azerbaijani terminology. The abbreviation is a non-standard variant as a term and does not actually describe the process accurately. It is possible from this point of view to use abbreviations and contractions terms as a national language first and as an international term secondly. Abbreviation refers to a linguistic event and involves the process of creating a short version of a syntactic structure of a word or word combination. The result of an abbreviation or contraction is an abbreviation or contraction. Both the linguistic phenomenon and its product (abbreviation) are used in a scientific style. Abbreviations are used in various functional styles in modern period. However, different aspects are revealed in the use of abbreviations in different styles. Abbreviations are used a lot in some styles and they are used comparatively less in other styles. Studies show that abbreviation in scientific style is somewhat widespread. It should also be noted that there are fields of science in which there is a greater need for abbreviations. The main purpose of creating an abbreviation is to shorten a multicomponent combination. The main motivation for abbreviating a word is the word's functionality. Acknowledging the names of physical units as abbreviations is to expand and simplify their usability. A common abbreviated system for units of measurement has been accepted in Physics. For example, meter - m, Ampere - A, Henry - Hn, Volt - V, Watt - W, etc.

As it is seen, the term creation process develops in connection with a scientific and technical process. Concepts are named during this process. A unique aspect of the term-creation process is the use of international elements. International elements expand the base of term creation. The potential possibilities of the language are widely used in the term-creation

process. The semantics of the word expands in some cases and semantic conversion and semantic compression occur in other cases. As a result, a scientific research plays a leading role in enriching the terminology of the field with new terms. The studies conducted on the basis of new terms recorded in scientific texts help to clarify the role of term-creation in scientific style. The analysis shows that the methods that manifest themselves in term-creation in a scientific style differ according to their specific characteristics.

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